

Why are qualifications frameworks so ineffective? The role of academic drift in their implementation in Bangladesh and Switzerland

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ABSTRACT

Based on an analysis of Bangladesh and Switzerland, and focusing on vocational education and training, the article discusses why qualifications frameworks often do not have the impact that policymakers expect them to have. Drawing on an historical-institutionalist reading of the literature, it argues, in general terms, that this lack of effective implementation stems from existing institutions and from key actors in the respective VET systems who cling to and benefit from these existing institutions. On a more specific level, the article adds to this institutionalist reading by arguing that ineffective implementation of NQFs needs to be interpreted in the broader context of educational expansion and the social conflicts manifested in this process. Particular attention should be paid to the phenomenon of academic drift, which, as the two case studies suggest, affects the implementation of NQFs in different ways.

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1. Introduction

National qualifications frameworks (NQFs) have spread rapidly around the world in the last three decades or so, with Fernie and Pilcher (2009) even speaking of a 'global tsunami' of NQFs. Undoubtedly, such frameworks have become a central element of a global policy toolkit for reforming education and training systems, in particular, vocational education and training (VET) systems, with which great hopes are associated (McGrath 2012). The frameworks are intended to contribute, for example, to the transparency of education systems or to increased international mobility between education systems and labour markets (Allais 2017a; Mikulec 2017; Raffe 2013). Given these ambitions, there is considerable interest in the extent to which these goals have been achieved, although the number of research papers on NQFs has declined somewhat in

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recent years¹ and the remaining studies suggest that the key objectives of NQFs have not been achieved (see e.g. Allais 2010, 2017a).

Despite strong evidence of the lack of impact of NQFs, not much research has systematically addressed the reasons for this. Despite there being evidence from a few studies, it has proved extremely difficult to investigate the impact of specific factors on the effectiveness of NQFs, mainly because of the complexity of the causal relationships, but also because the objectives that NQFs are intended to achieve are extremely diverse (Allais 2017c; Pilcher, Fernie, and Smith 2017). It is therefore more realistic to develop a theoretical framework against which the creation and implementation of qualifications frameworks can be interpreted. This article aims to contribute to the development of precisely such a framework with the help of a comparative case study.

The comparative study focuses on two countries – Bangladesh and Switzerland – which have received little attention in the literature on NQFs, this being one of the reasons they were chosen for the study. Both countries have established NQF for VET qualifications since around 2010: Bangladesh's so-called National Technical and Vocational Qualifications Framework (NTVQF) (which was replaced by the Bangladesh National Qualifications Framework in 2021); and Switzerland's so-called National Framework for Vocational Qualifications (Swiss VET NQF).

These two cases are interpreted against the background of a historical-institutionalist theoretical framework, a framework that has become very important in comparative VET research (Graf and Lohse 2022) and that plays, as will be shown in the next section, an implicit role in existing studies on the lack of impact of NQFs.

2. Review of research on NQFs

The following sections first presents relevant findings from various strands of NQF research and then conducts a literature review of readings which provide an institutionalist view of the lack of implementation.

2.1. Key findings from the literature about NQFs and their impact

A first finding from the literature relevant to this article is that NQFs have spread globally without any convincing evidence of their effectiveness (Allais 2010; Raffe 2013). Starting with countries with so-called first-generation frameworks, which initially focused primarily on VET, there was a real 'NQF[eu]phoria' (Raffe 2013, 144), which subsumed more and more countries and went beyond VET. This was supported in European countries and those in Europe's neighbourhood by the European Union's decision to establish the European Qualifications Framework for Lifelong Learning (EQF) (Elken 2015; European Commission 2008).

Second, the literature shows that these frameworks have very different objectives and that they also vary widely between countries. As Markowitsch and Dębowski (2022, 403) note, a common goal of NQFs is certainly to 'promote transparency within or between qualifications systems'. In many cases, however, countries formulate much more far-reaching objectives: NQFs should also contribute to the permeability of education systems, enable the recognition of prior learning (RPL), facilitate the mobility of workers between countries or increase the labour market orientation of educational opportunities. In this context, Raffe (2013) has suggested distinguishing between descriptive NQFs on the one hand, and more reformist or transformative frameworks on the other. In any case, as Pilcher, Fernie, and Smith (2017) argue, the fact that the objectives associated with NQFs are so diverse makes it difficult to analyse their effectiveness, especially across national borders (see also Allais 2017c).

Third, despite the difficulties in analysing the effectiveness of NQFs, there is a consensus in the literature that in many cases the objectives of such frameworks have not been achieved. This applies first to the goal of transparency: many qualifications frameworks are written in such technical language that they are difficult for non-experts, such as employers, to understand and therefore not used by them during recruitment (Oliver and Walpole 2017; Raffe 2013). In some countries like France, links do exist between qualifications frameworks and recruitment practices. However, these are due to the fact that the frameworks adopt the existing hierarchical structure of qualifications, which is largely respected in the labour market (Allais 2017b). At the same time, regional frameworks, for example in Europe or Africa, have done little to facilitate international labour mobility. This is because employers are unfamiliar with the respective frameworks (Bohlinger 2019; Marock and Allais 2022). There is also little evidence of a contribution of the frameworks to the recognition of prior learning (RPL) or to permeability between non-formal and formal education (Maurer 2023). However, there is evidence that NQFs have at least partially contributed to improving permeability between different parts of education systems, such as between VET and higher education (Allais 2010).

2.2. Explanations for the failure of NQFs

The existing literature also addresses the key question of this article by discussing why the frameworks are so ineffective. Since the arguments of these contributions explicitly or at least implicitly refer to approaches from comparative education, three such approaches are briefly outlined below.

A first approach is the neo-institutionalist perspective, which has gained prominence in analysing the global diffusion of educational models. Neo-institutionalists see this diffusion as a result of global norms ('institutions') that compel governments to justify their respective national education policies

(Meyer and Ramirez 2009). These norms often lead to institutional 'isomorphism' (Meyer and Rowan 1977, 346), which, however, results only in superficial changes and subsequently in a 'decoupling' (Meyer and Rowan 1977, 357) between national regulations (aligned with international norms) and the actions at implementation level.

A second approach also addresses the global dissemination of educational models, but from a more actor-centred perspective on the lenders and borrowers of such models (Phillips and Ochs 2003; Steiner-Khamsi 2012). Theorists in this tradition have examined on the one hand, the considerable weight and influence of specific lenders of educational models, such as multi- and bilateral donors, and highlighted their diverse political and economic motives for engaging in lending. On the other hand, this literature has also explored the motives of borrowers and has emphasised that, during the implementation process, global models are often significantly appropriated or 'indigenised' (Phillips and Ochs 2003). In this context, Silova (2005) refers to a 'hijacking' of policies, where initiatives promoted by the global educational community in lower- and middle-income countries are repurposed by local policymakers to serve their own interests.

A third approach, finally, is that of historical institutionalism, which has become highly influential in comparative research on skill formation and offers a bridge between the two perspectives mentioned earlier. From a historical-institutionalist perspective, actors and institutions are strongly interdependent. While institutional developments are seen as being path-dependent, actors also play a central role: they not only reinforce the 'stickiness' of institutions through positive feedback but can also advocate for the creation of new institutions, which typically result in only gradual changes to the existing system (Mayntz 2002; Polman and Alons 2021). Such incremental changes take various forms (Streeck and Thelen 2005): in the case of 'drift,' for instance, existing institutions gradually lose importance in favour of others. Academic drift, for example, refers to the increasing prominence of academic upper-secondary and higher education (often at the expense of upper-secondary VET) as well as the growing significance of general subjects within VET to enhance educational mobility opportunities (Busemeyer and Trampusch 2012).

Arguments from these three theoretical perspectives are now also reflected in the literature on NQFs. This is particularly explicit in Bohlinger (2019), who interprets the global diffusion of qualifications frameworks through the lens of neo-institutionalism as 'institutional isomorphism' and then identifies a decoupling between policy-level regulations and their implementation. From this perspective, the ineffectiveness of NQFs results from their alignment with global templates, rendering the specific national context largely irrelevant.

Arguments from the more actor-centred perspective on educational borrowing and lending, which also places greater emphasis on analysing actual implementation processes, are particularly evident in Allais' work (see e.g. Allais 2003,

2014). This is especially reflected in her considerations on NQF designs, which, in her view, are shaped by neo-liberal assumptions about the relationships between education and labour markets held by both lenders and borrowers. At the same time, Allais attributes the limited impact of NQFs primarily to the way real labour markets in many countries are structured, which often contradicts these neo-liberal assumptions and is at odds with the over-specified competence standards that often characterise NQFs (Allais 2007).

This argument, which emphasises the ‘stickiness’ of existing institutions in line with historical institutionalism, is also found in the work of other authors, such as Raffe (2015). He points to the importance of an ‘institutional logic’ in labour markets and education systems, which regulates how qualifications are acquired and used, but which thus runs counter to the ‘intrinsic logic’ of NQFs. Similarly, Clement (2016) underscores the importance of existing institutions, too, but she also highlights the significant influence of individual actors, such as certifying institutions and labour unions, who benefit from existing regulations and thus complicate the implementation of NQFs.

3. Outline of the case study approach

3.1. A historical-institutionalist analytical framework

The literature review reveals that the ineffectiveness of qualifications frameworks is not explicitly explained by a single theoretical perspective in existing NQF research. However, while the role of institutions and actors is assessed differently in the analysis of policy design, the review suggests that key contributions to the literature explaining the lack of effectiveness of frameworks implicitly adopt a historical institutionalist argument.

This leads to the following hypothesis:

NQFs are not as effective as hoped because, first, existing institutions at national and sub-national levels (e.g. in education or employment) hinder their implementation and second, key actors defend the form and position of existing qualifications within the respective education systems and labour markets.

The aim of this paper is to discuss this hypothesis based on two case studies, adopting an explicitly historical-institutionalist perspective. The focus will be on the following:

- (a) the institutional context of the NQF and its historical development, particularly regarding the education and vocational education systems as well as the main qualifications and their institutional embedding in the labour market;
- (b) the national regulations concerning the NQF;

- (c) the regulations established in the context of the implementation of the NQF; and
- (d) the key actors who play a critical role in shaping and implementing the NQF.

3.2. Justification of the case selection

The two cases were selected because they represent contrasting contexts in several respects. On the one hand – and quite evidently – they differ in their global positioning: while Bangladesh, a country in the global South, remains characterised by poverty despite significant economic and social transformations, and implements major reforms largely supported by bilateral and multi-lateral donors (World Bank 2023), Switzerland, situated in the global North, is affluent and undertakes reforms with relatively greater autonomy (Bernauer and Walter 2023).

The two countries also differ substantially in their VET systems. In Switzerland, the proportion of upper-secondary students enrolled in VET programmes is very high by international standards, as is the share of VET students completing apprenticeships under company contracts (BFS 2024). Consequently, vocational qualifications hold significant relevance for labour market access (Emmenegger and Seitzl 2020; Gonon and Maurer 2012). In contrast, VET in Bangladesh, particularly at the upper-secondary level, involves much lower enrolment rates, is predominantly school-based, and is rarely organised in collaboration with employers. As a result, VET qualifications play a very limited role in the Bangladeshi labour market (Haolader, Foyso, and Clement 2017; Maurer, Haolader, and Shimu 2023).

3.3. Data basis

The comparative case study builds its argument on two types of data that facilitate an examination of the development and implementation of NQFs. First, it analyses textual documents, particularly policy strategy papers, legal texts, and curricula. For Bangladesh, the author's involvement in various academic research projects between 2006 and 2024 provided access to such documents (Maurer 2011; Maurer and Rabbani 2021). These projects addressed diverse aspects of the country's VET system, examining its policy framework while also shedding light on the development of the qualifications framework. For Switzerland, statements from key stakeholders on the draft ordinance on the Swiss VET NQF were also analysed. Second, the article draws upon qualitative interviews. For Bangladesh, eight interviews were conducted with representatives of authorities, training providers, business associations, and enterprises. These were part of a larger set of interviews ($n = 34$) conducted within one of the aforementioned research projects (Maurer and Rabbani 2021). The interviews

cited here are those which include statements on the qualifications framework. In Switzerland, three interviews were conducted specifically for this article: one with a representative of a federal authority, one with a trade union representative, and one with a key representative of higher VET. The smaller number of interviews in Switzerland reflects the availability of written statements from key stakeholders, as mentioned earlier. Both types of data were analysed using qualitative content analysis (Gläser and Laudel 2019; Kuckartz 2018).

4. The case of Bangladesh

Bangladesh has undergone enormous economic and social change since gaining independence from Pakistan in 1971. A few decades ago, it was still one of the poorest countries in the world; now it is a lower middle-income country, although poverty is still widespread (World Bank 2023). The garment industry has played a special role in the country's development and is now by far the largest export sector, employing more than 4 million workers (Rahman 2023).

Access to education has been greatly expanded, especially since the 1980s. While a large proportion of the population did not have access to primary education at that time (Dove 1983), the adult literacy rate is now around 72%, and access to upper secondary education (Senior Secondary Certificate SSC and Higher Secondary Certificate HSC) and higher education has grown significantly (BANBEIS 2023; World Bank 2023). As a result of the expansion of education, the importance of general education qualifications in the labour market has increased (Kalam and Shimu 2020).

VET was primarily established in Bangladesh in the form of technician programmes first under British rule, later under Pakistan, and even after independence. These programmes offered limited opportunities for educational mobility, making them relatively unpopular. In the 1990s, two VET programmes were reformed to include general education; the SSC Voc and HSC Voc programmes entitle graduates to enter various tertiary-level programmes, which is why they are mainly used today. Leading to a pronounced academic drift in the country's VET system, these programmes have become the most popular ones, although they are still a second choice at the upper secondary level. In this context, formal VET (whose share at upper secondary level was 10.8% in 2022) is mainly school-based and academically oriented, and its qualifications play a small role in the labour market (Kalam and Shimu 2020; Maurer 2012; Maurer, Haolader, and Shimu 2023; UIS 2023).

4.1. Development of a transformative qualifications framework

In a global context where the focus of bi- and multilateral aid shifted back towards VET after many years of prioritising basic education, the European Union in Bangladesh began financing a major VET project in 2006, which was

implemented with technical support from the International Labour Organization (ILO) and ultimately led to the formulation of a Skills Development Policy in 2011 (European Commission 2006; Ministry of Education 2011). The new policy began due to criticism that the country's VET system was not sufficiently labour-market-oriented and accessible to the poorest (European Commission 2006; Int BD 1), and it proposed reform including many elements of what McGrath (2012) calls the global VET policy toolbox. The establishment of a qualifications framework, the National Technical and Vocational Qualifications Framework (NTVQF) (Government of Bangladesh 2013), was the central element of this reform, linked to many other initiatives, such as the introduction of competency-based curricula and RPL, thereby adopting a similar approach to that of the European Union with the EQF.

From the beginning of the reform process, the international community had high hopes for the NTVQF. The ambition was to create a ' [...] system of [...] qualifications and curricula' that would be 'demand-driven, modular and competency-based enabling the underprivileged groups [...] to access recognised skills training' (European Commission 2006 16). With the definition of the framework in 2011, the objectives became even more diverse: the framework was intended to 'improve the quality and consistency of nationally recognised qualifications' or 'to increase opportunities for students by broadening programme and progression pathways' (Ministry of Education 2011 14–15). The new system was to be administered by a new authority, now called the National Skills Development Commission, reporting directly to the Prime Minister (Government of Bangladesh 2018).

The apparent goal of what, in the words of Raffe (2013), can be described as a 'transformative' NQF, was to fundamentally overhaul VET in Bangladesh. This ambition went so far as to suggest that the existing formal VET programmes would no longer play a role, which is illustrated by the fact that, at least for a while, these programmes were no longer mentioned in some official reports on VET (see e.g. Government of Bangladesh 2015).

What was particularly new about the NTVQF for Bangladesh was its two pre-vocational levels (ILO 2012; Ministry of Education 2011, 16). Their main purpose was to improve access to VET, as there was previously no route into formal VET for those who had not completed eight years of basic education. In particular, people with work experience were now to be given access to such a pre-vocational qualification, not least through RPL (BTEB 2012b; Maurer and Morshed 2022).

4.2. *Decoupling of framework from the existing VET system*

The new NTVQF remained essentially unconnected to the existing VET system, even though the qualifications were now comparable on paper. This lack of

connection was also the main reason why the intended effects largely failed to materialise.

The disconnect was evident in the position of the new competency standards: they were produced by a newly created unit ('CBT Cell') within the country's main VET authority (Bangladesh Technical Education Board BTEB), in collaboration with representatives of the private sector (e.g. BTEB 2012a; van Asseldonk et al. 2013). Indeed, these new competency-based standards were then used, but mainly by commercial VET providers who were now expected to run state-recognised, mostly privately funded courses (Government of Bangladesh 2013). However, these new competency standards were not widely adopted in existing formal VET programmes, particularly the SSC Voc and HSC Voc programmes. In order to ensure access to post-secondary and tertiary levels (polytechnics and technical universities), these programmes remained largely unchanged, with a limited focus on practical training (BTEB 2015a; 2015b; Int BD 2). Unsurprisingly, the qualifications defined in the NTVQF play no role at all in the labour market (Int BD 3–5).

The NTVQF has not made VET more accessible to the socially disadvantaged either: a completed basic education is still required for access to formal VET. At the same time, the above-mentioned private training courses based on the new qualification standards either do not improve access to the labour market for the socially disadvantaged or are too expensive for them (ADB 2015; Int BD 6–8).

At first glance, this lack of impact of the qualifications framework can be explained by the fact that it was created on the basis of a global template (see McGrath 2012) which was insufficiently adapted to the Bangladeshi context. However, this is not a sufficient explanation. Clearly, key actors in the Bangladeshi VET system did not support the main objectives of the NTVQF, and the institutional foundations of the existing formal VET system were at odds with the framework. Indeed, there is a strong consensus among key stakeholders that access to formal VET requires completion of basic education (Int BD 2). They have therefore never agreed to one of the key objectives of the NTVQF that has always been so relevant to the international community: that of increasing access to VET for those who lack basic education. In addition, VET, which is often seen as dysfunctional and not practice-oriented, meets a strong social demand: precisely because vocational qualifications play a small role in the labour market, many people see VET as an alternative route to tertiary education, and there are few incentives for key actors to make VET more vocational (Maurer, Haolader, and Shimu 2023).

Despite these obvious implementation problems, the government has since raised expectations of the framework once again by introducing the Bangladesh National Qualifications Framework (BNQF) in 2021 (Ministry of Education 2021), again with the support of the donor community, including the ILO. Despite all the difficulties in improving the comparability of programmes within VET alone,

the BNQF is intended to cover all sectors of the education system, including higher education.

5. The case of Switzerland

VET continues to play a very central role in the Swiss education system. Few other countries have such a high proportion of VET at upper secondary level (66% in 2022/2023), and in no other country is the share of company-based apprenticeships (60%) in upper-secondary VET so high (BFS 2024; Kriesi et al. 2022). The system is often described as permeable, but it is also highly socially selective, with access to upper-secondary VET and then to higher education strongly correlated with the socio-economic status of the parents of the young people concerned (Gomensoro and Meyer 2021; Kost 2018).

At the same time, there is growing public criticism, for example from trade unions, that the salaries of VET graduates are no longer sufficient to live on (SGB 2022). While the legitimacy of the strong position of VET remains high in many parts of the country and among key actors in the education system, social demand for upper secondary general education is growing, even though academic drift in upper secondary still remains moderate by international standards (Markowitsch 2021; SKBF 2023).

In addition, the position of higher VET, i.e. those programmes that are open to upper secondary VET graduates without an extended general education and which are officially referred to as tertiary-level 'professional education' in Switzerland, are a subject of debate. In particular, their positioning in relation to bachelor's and master's degrees offered by universities, which are becoming increasingly important in the labour market depending on the economic sector, has been controversial for many years (Schmid and Gonon 2013).

5.1. A descriptive framework for VET qualifications

The Swiss VET NQF was developed in the context of the country's European strategy (Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft 2010). One aspect of this strategy is the adoption of some of the EU's key education policy instruments, including the EQF, which aims, among other things, to improve the comparability of qualifications across Europe and promote the transparency of education systems, particularly with a view to strengthening the transnational mobility within the European labour market (Cedefop 2018; Elken 2015; European Commission 2008; Mikulec 2017).

The specificity of the Swiss implementation strategy was that in contrast to Germany, for example (AK DQR 2016) two qualifications frameworks were developed, one for universities, for levels 6–8 (Bachelor/Master/PHD) (swissuniversities 2021), and a National Qualifications Framework for VET qualifications (VET NQF) (Bundesrat 2014). This approach of creating two separate frameworks

was criticised early on by the universities (CRUS 2012), but it gave VET stakeholders significantly more room for manoeuvre.

This VET NQF was not aimed at creating new qualifications or actually reforming VET – and thus ‘descriptive’ in nature (see Raffe 2013). From the outset, however, it was seen by key stakeholders as an instrument to better position Swiss VET, especially higher VET. The NQF ordinance makes this very clear: the framework is intended to ‘express the high value of Swiss VET [...]’, ‘promote the social reputation and appreciation of VET compared to academic education [...]’ and ‘strengthen the international reputation of higher VET [...]’ (Bundesrat 2014 5; translation by the author). Although the framework was also intended to promote international labour mobility, it focused particularly on ‘improving the opportunities of skilled workers and managers trained in Switzerland when seeking employment abroad and with foreign companies in Switzerland’. Facilitating the mobility of workers with foreign qualifications was thus never a central objective of the Swiss VET NQF. This seems understandable in the broader context of the political debates on labour migration in Switzerland, which were particularly controversial at the time (Gallerano 2014). However, there is no doubt that the ordinance’s focus on the mobility of Swiss VET graduates was not fully in line with the EQF’s overarching objectives.

Like the EQF, the Swiss VET NQF consists of eight levels to which vocational qualifications (there are several hundred) are assigned on the basis of a catalogue of criteria. By classifying the qualifications in the VET NQF, they have also been referenced to the EQF since 2015 (SBFI 2015). In contrast to Germany, for example, the qualifications were initially classified at the request of the relevant associations, which had to justify their proposal with regard to the classification criteria, whereby these applications were reviewed by the authorities in an ‘appreciative’ manner (Int CH 1). Over time, this process proved too time-consuming for the associations, so qualifications are now generally assigned to levels in a highly standardised way (SBFI 2018).

The classification of higher VET qualifications is particularly noteworthy. Diplomas awarded by colleges of higher vocational education and training (PETs) were classified at level 6, which corresponds to a bachelor’s degree according to the EQF, such as the diploma for nurses, while so-called advanced federal vocational diplomas, such as the diploma for master carpenters, were classified at level 7, which corresponds to a master’s degree. Very few qualifications have been placed at level 8, which corresponds to a doctorate, such as the diploma of expert in accounting and controlling (SBFI 2024).

5.2. Small impact from an EQF perspective

The impact of the Swiss VET NQF has been analysed only marginally. In one of the few academic articles on the subject, based primarily on a global assessment, Martins (2022) came to the conclusion that the ‘NQF has failed’. Even

within the federal administration, the view is that the NQF has had little impact (Int CH 1). Certainly, the impact with regard to central objectives of the EQF is low: the levels of the qualifications framework are hardly known in the labour market and they are not taken into account in the collective labour agreements – both trade unions and employers’ associations would oppose this idea (SAV 2012; SGB 2012; Int CH 2). Accordingly, the NQF certainly does not make a significant contribution to the transnational mobility of employees.

Nevertheless, the VET NQF is relevant from a policy perspective, as it is utilised by representatives of higher VET seeking to enhance the position of these qualifications relative to academic higher education qualifications (see Criblez and Kraus 2022). In fact, they have long called for (existing) higher VET qualifications to be labelled as Professional Bachelor’s and Professional Master’s, hoping that such new titles would increase their attractiveness. For many years, this proposal was rejected by federal authorities, who were ware that universities would be extremely critical of it; they hoped instead that the introduction of the VET NQF would enhance the attractiveness of higher VET (SBFI 2014).

However, as the framework remained largely unknown to employers, the authorities have run out of arguments to prevent such titles, especially since they are convinced that higher VET needs to be strengthened. At the same time, thanks to the VET NQF, the representatives of higher VET can now easily argue that these qualifications are comparable to academic higher education qualifications at the Bachelor’s and Master’s levels also from an international perspective (Int CH 3). Expectedly, the federal authorities finally gave in and proposed a reform, yet to be adopted by parliament, to supplement the existing higher VET qualifications with the titles Professional Bachelor and Professional Master (Bundesrat 2024; SBFI 2023).

6. Discussion of case study findings from a comparative perspective

6.1. Confirmation of key findings from the existing literature

In both countries, as in many others (e.g. Allais 2014; Bohlinger 2019), the qualifications frameworks were developed against the backdrop of a global template for such frameworks and to serve the aim of international cooperation, leading to what neo-institutionalists have labelled ‘institutional isomorphism’. In Bangladesh, this occurred through the lending efforts of bilateral and multi-lateral donors and resulted in, what (Raffe 2013) could be labelled, a ‘transformative’ framework that was aimed to overhaul the entire VET system. In Switzerland, the framework was developed in the context of political efforts to achieve convergence with the European Union in certain policy areas – and was intended to have a mainly ‘descriptive’ (Raffe 2013) function to map the existing formal qualifications.

The comparison also shows that the frameworks have so far had little significant impact, thus confirming existing findings. In both countries, the frameworks have not contributed to permeability within education systems, nor do the classifications have any significance in the labour market. What neo-institutionalists label as ‘decoupling’ is evident in the case of Bangladesh in an almost grotesque form, with the framework being entirely detached from the existing VET system. What, in light of Allais (2014) contributions, could be seen as a success of the neoliberal education policy is the fact that private providers were given the opportunity to offer state-recognised programmes; yet, from the EU’s perspective, the unachieved improvement in access to VET would have been a far more important goal. In Switzerland, the framework has made little contribution to the goals of the overarching EQF, but it has been used, if not ‘hijacked’ (Silova 2005), by key actors with the aim to better position higher VET.

Finally, the comparison shows, that the qualifications frameworks in both countries are not as effective as hoped because of the path-dependent development of the skill formation systems in the two countries. This confirms the hypotheses presented after the literature review (Allais 2014; Clement 2016; Raffe 2013) as well as using the historical-institutionalist approach. Existing institutions at national and sub-national levels hinder implementation, notably because these institutions are sustained by key actors who wish to maintain the form and position of existing qualifications in the respective education systems and labour markets.

6.2. Impact of academic drift

Going beyond findings from the existing literature on NQFs, the comparative analysis, however, also suggests that the lack of effectiveness of the frameworks in both cases can only be understood by taking into account academic drift. In this way, the paper specifically distinguishes itself from Allais (2014) perspective, which emphasises that this ineffectiveness is mainly due to the incorrect assumptions about the relationship between the education system and the labour market that are associated with NQFs.

The impact of academic drift on NQF implementation is particularly evident in the case of Bangladesh, where the drift has significantly shaped the development of formal VET since the 1990s. The 2011 reform, which centred on the NTVQF, was intended to reverse this trend – and above all improve access to VET. As a result, key actors feared a potential critical juncture that would undermine the focus of upper secondary VET on preparing students for post-secondary and tertiary education – and strongly opposed the entire reform. In Switzerland, on the other hand, the framework has been used by key players to curb academic drift. They want the vast majority of upper secondary students to enrol in VET and therefore have seen the framework as a means of better positioning higher VET vis-à-vis academic higher education.

It is evident that in both cases, a phenomenon which has been scarcely addressed in the NQF literature has had a significant impact on implementation. This may be surprising, as academic drift is discussed not only in the historical-institutionalist literature on skill formation (Busemeyer and Trampusch 2012) but also in many other contributions addressing the development of VET systems (Grubb and Lazerson 2012; Rauner 2012; Smeby 2014). This literature not only highlights that academic drift is a central trend in many education systems but also challenges the value of primarily labour market-oriented, traditionally often terminal VET in many countries (Markowitsch and Hefler 2019). Academic drift is therefore often associated with conflict, and, as the cases of Bangladesh and Switzerland demonstrate, such conflicts have had a very direct impact on the implementation of NQFs. It would be important, therefore, to examine the role of academic drift in the implementation of NQFs in further studies.

6.3. Analysing NQFs in their relation to educational expansion

These insights into the significance of academic drift suggest that studies of the implementation of NQFs should take a systematic look at the process of educational expansion as a whole, within which the mentioned conflicts arise. A purely historical-institutionalist analytical framework may not suffice for this, as research on skill formation from this theoretical perspective tends to overly focus – in line with neo-Marxist theory – on the ‘classical’ political-economic actors, and therefore neglects those institutions and actors that evolve dynamically during the process of educational expansion (Maurer 2024). Thus, it would be worthwhile to reconsider the work of Margaret Archer, which places this dynamic at the centre of analyses on education systems’ development (Archer 1979; Archer and Morgan 2020). The core argument of this work is that the supply of and demand for education often grow in tandem, so that higher and higher levels of educational attainment become indispensable for participation in the labour market. In such cases, Archer speaks of a period of educational inflation – a phenomenon that is clearly relevant to the design and implementation of NQFs in the two contexts analysed here.

However, orienting future analyses of the transformation of VET systems in general and the implementation of NQFs in particular to Archer’s work would not mean that a historical-institutionalist perspective becomes irrelevant. Rather, both perspectives share a focus on the interdependence of social agency and institutions, the significance of which has also been confirmed by the present study.

7. Conclusions for policy making

Based on case studies of countries whose NQFs have not yet been systematically researched, the present study reaffirms a key policy-relevant finding from the literature (Allais 2011, 2017b; Raffe 2013): NQFs tend to be less effective than hoped. Against this background, education policy should therefore be, once more, advised to pursue realistic goals and to seek results from comparative research, especially at a time when many citizens doubt the legitimacy of state action. This is especially true for education policies in the global South, whose priorities are often strongly influenced by models and assumptions from the global North. There needs to be a much greater commitment to understanding the complex relationships between education and labour markets – including the role of increasing academic drift in many education systems. Unfortunately, the opposite is often the case.

Educational experts who advise authorities have an important role to play in policymaking. They should make clear what is known, and what is not. However, in the case of qualifications frameworks, many of them have helped to formulate assumptions about impact that should not have been made in the light of the limited evidence available at the time.

However, if the objectives are not achieved through NQFs, this does not mean that these objectives are not relevant. For example, creating permeability or recognising prior learning are legitimate concerns that can, however, be promoted independently of NQFs. In any case – and this is another finding of this article – such reforms require an approach that takes seriously the lines of conflict in the process of educational expansion.
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Note

1. Based on Google Scholar searches for ‘qualifications frameworks’ for the years 2000–2023; the number of publications peaked in 2015 (626).

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